

LIMNOLOGY AROUND (A MORE EXTREME) WORLD: SPAIN

Biodiversity and ecosystem functioning when rivers run dry

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Rivers and streams in arid or semi-arid regions often experience periodic low flows or complete drying lasting from a few days to long hydrological periods. These river systems, known as intermittent or temporary, play vital roles in their landscapes by connecting aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems and supporting a unique biodiversity. The biota of these systems is adapted to fluctuating water availability and enduring conditions, ranging from episodic flash floods to stagnant or dry phases. Because these hydrological oscillations are largely predictable, organisms have evolved diverse strategies to adapt, such as migration, refugia seeking, synchronizing reproductive cycles, or employing specific morphological or physiological mechanisms to cope with wet-dry conditions. Consequently, a wide array of specialized organisms, including microbes, invertebrates, fish, and mammals, exhibit unique developmental patterns and survival strategies in these systems.

Temporary streams and rivers display characteristic patterns of local (alpha) and spatial or temporal (beta) biodiversity, which are closely linked to their hydrological phases. These phases transition from flowing to contracting and drying, often in rapid succession, and later to recovery phases when favorable conditions return. Although

the recovery phase, beta diversity may either increase through recolonization by various species or decrease through the re-establishment of common species. Because these systems dry and recover at different times and to varying degrees, their beta diversity often exceeds that of permanent systems, which tend to be more stable and homogeneous.

Temporary streams and rivers perform essential ecosystem functions, their relative importance changing across hydrological phases. Alternating wet and dry phases create pulses of materials and energy that differ from those in permanent systems. During dry phases, organic materials such as leaves and branches accumulate, break down, and mobilize upon rewetting to fuel microbial and detritivore activity. Primary productivity during flow periods is similar to that in permanent rivers, although it intensifies during low flow and ceases during desiccation because of algal die-off. The desiccation phase reduces gross primary production (GPP) and increases CO₂ emissions (Sepp *et al.*, 2024). And then, the rewetting of dry sediments can release pulses of CO₂ and CH₄ emissions, with the intensity depending on the availability of organic matter. These findings highlight the role of temporary streams in greenhouse gas production, which should not be underestimated.

These features establish temporary rivers and streams as hotspots of biodiversity and ecological functions and play critical roles in the resilience of arid and semi-arid landscapes. Although some patterns are well understood, many ecological and evolutionary aspects remain unknown. Significant research efforts, such as [Dryver](#), [StreamCLIMES](#), and [AIMS](#), aim to unravel their biodiversity values and functions. Other initiatives (e.g., <https://valuing-nature.net/TemporaryRiverNC>) emphasize the biodiversity value of these ecosystems in temperate areas, where intermittent systems are becoming more frequent.

Although these systems have enormous ecological and evolutionary value, they can also offer insights into the impacts of human-driven alterations on water flow. Human intervention in the hydrological cycle is increasing, significantly affecting global watercourses (Messenger *et al.*, 2021). Climate change, water abstraction, and regulation, which affect both surface and groundwater, have caused many formerly permanent river systems to experience altered flow dynamics or even complete flow cessation in certain areas or during specific periods. Natural temporary rivers exhibit high resilience to predictable water flow

River Siurana, NE Spain, during spring

many studies have focused on biological diversity during wet phases, the overall biodiversity present throughout all hydrological phases remains underestimated. Typically, alpha diversity declines during the drying phase, yet specialist taxa capable of forming dispersal or dormant stages (e.g., seeds, eggs, or cysts) sustain richness. During flowing periods, alpha and beta diversities in temporary systems are comparable to those in permanent systems. Conversely, during

interruptions; however, the rise in unpredictable conditions in once-permanent watercourses can severely compromise their ecological integrity. Hydrological alterations due to extractive water use are often accompanied by additional impacts, such as water pollution and invasive species, which are exacerbated by habitat homogenization and nearby human activities. These cumulative pressures threaten the biodiversity, ecological

River Algars (NE Spain) during the contracting phase (late spring)

functions, and critical services provided by these systems, such as clean drinking water and flood regulation. Evaluating the responses of altered permanent rivers in comparison with natural temporary systems could offer valuable perspectives for sustainable management.

River conservation should prioritize temporary watercourses, as they may serve as “living laboratories” to study ecological and evolutionary processes shaped by wet-dry cycles. In certain regions such as the tropics and Antarctica, the isolated nature of temporary streams and rivers can drive genetic differentiation and speciation. Ecological traits, such as rapid growth, high fecundity, and desiccation-resistant life stages, are likely underexplored and may yet be discovered. Our understanding of these systems remains incomplete, particularly regarding the structure of their trophic webs, which are shaped by strong links between the aquatic and terrestrial states. Numerous unanswered questions highlight the need for dedicated research and underscore the importance of raising the awareness of these ecosystems. Fully incorporating them into conservation and management plans is essential to preserve their ecological and evolutionary significance.

References:

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